

The Organizational Landscape: Unprecedented Change?

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Abstract

The book, *Dynamic Administration: The Collected Papers of Mary Parker Follett* (1982), is a posthumously published collection of Miss Follett's speeches and articles. The purpose for the descriptive review* of this book is to explore Mary Parker Follett's (1868-1933) existing studies; then to present her research in relation to the "challenges facing all forms of organized enterprises today" (Fox & Urwick, Eds., 1982, Introduction).

- A descriptive book review "presents the content and structure of a book as objectively as possible, describing essential information about a book's purpose and authority" (USC Libraries, n.d.).
- "The most important element of a review...is that it allows one to to enter into dialogue and discussion with the work's creator and other audiences" (The Writing Center, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, n.d.).

Mary Parker Follett (1868-1933), described the business landscape, as follows: "In a time of unprecedented change and intensified competition for physical and human resources on all levels, there is reason to ask how we can energize dormant talent, control without stifling, resolve conflicts that can frustrate the ablest of [people], inspire commitment to constructive lines of action, and supply a managerial leadership worthy of the challenges facing all forms of organized enterprises today" (Fox & Urwick, Eds., 1982, Introduction).

Follett "believed that anyone with a firm grip of two fundamental concepts;" universal fact and universal goals, "had a clear blueprint for constructive leadership in the most confusing situation" (Fox & Urwick, Eds., 1982, p XXXIII).

The first of her fundamental concepts, universal fact, recognizes "that there is always a mutual influence between the parties to an interaction" (Fox & Urwick, Eds., 1982, Introduction). That is, there is a unique store of "knowledge, values, wishes, interests, and action tendencies of each participant" in every situation. Hence, our attention on the immediate participants includes "all the relationships that have any bearing on their thinking" (Fox & Urwick, Eds., 1982, p 28).

Second, she defines universal goal as integration, or "differences which come together in a way that produces a new form." Miss Follett elaborates further by using the term coordination as being the "principle of integration as it applies to the problems of managing people in a human group having a common purpose" (Fox & Urwick, Eds., 1982, p XXV).

Nowadays, organizations are challenged with maintaining their position in a dynamic global market while faced with unprecedented change and intensified competition for physical and human resources on all levels. All forms of organized enterprises, from the large 'box' stores to small neighborhood shops; and on to the manufacturers and service providers are being affected.

A contributing factor is the bottleneck in shipping parts needed for production and then again for the finished product. Furthermore, the voice of the dwindling supply of labor, ranging from where and how to work to family priorities, is impacting a range of business decisions. On a related note, the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce and their job responsibilities are evolving in ways that influence the way that work is done; thus, the foundation of the organizational structure, the business units and their interrelated functions, are affected, too. (Zeller, 2017).

Overall, the external and internal environments are having an effect on marketability and profit. The challenges, numerous and complex, include: How to continually address changes in the external and internal environments while maintaining a competitive position in the evolving global market? What can be done to insure continuity in supply chains, from the point of production to the consumer? What can be done to effectively attract; to meet personal and professional

goals; and to retain human resources? What leadership is needed to proactively activate responses to the challenges of the constantly evolving environment?

Discussion Points

Mary Parker Follett, sought to develop and to apply answers to the real world business questions: "How can we energize dormant talent, control without stifling, resolve conflicts that can frustrate the ablest of [people], inspire commitment to constructive lines of action, and supply a managerial leadership worthy of the challenges facing all forms of organized enterprises today?" (Fox & Urwick, Eds., 1982, Introduction).

Though written in a much different time, Mary Parker Follett presents some sound direction that serves to inform and to guide the organizations of today.

Point #1:

Mary Parker Follett: Integration

Follett identifies the first step in integration as bringing the differences into the open. However, she also recognizes that "many situations are decidedly complex, involving numerous and varied, overlapping activities" (Fox & Urwick, Eds., 1982, p. 11). Hence, she suggests that when identifying the differences, to be aware that "the highest lights in a situation are not always those which are most indicative of the real issues involved" (Fox & Urwick, Eds., 1982, p. 11).

Current Business Challenge: Toyota

Toyota, "often referred to as the gold standard of the automobile industry", suffered a setback in 2009 / 2010 when the company had to recall 8 million of its vehicles due to an unintended acceleration problem (Saylor Academy, 2012; Zeller, 2016). The organizational structure, described as being based on a strict seniority hierarchy with centralized power, where "authority is generally not delegated within the company", provides some insight as to the handling of the crisis (Saylor Academy, 2012; Zeller, 2016). The hesitancy from the lower ranks to pass along any bad news or suggestions for improvement contributed to the crisis. Even when made aware of the problem, decisions by the senior hierarchy were held as the 'gold standard'. (Zeller, 2016).

Point #2:

Mary Parker Follett: Communications

Follett questioned the challenges of communicating orders and identified the issue as one of "utmost importance for business administration." She asked how orders should be conveyed "when the number of employees are as large and as widely scattered as in the case of the Elevated and Telephone employees." Follett wondered how the people at the top of such a large organization managed to "get their wishes across to so many widely scattered people" (Fox & Urwick, Eds., 1982, p. 39).

Current Business Challenge: Communications in a Hybrid (Virtual / Traditional) Work Environment

Transmitting knowledge; e.g. orders, instructions, announcements, etc; whether in a traditional workforce or a hybrid virtual / traditional workforce will be affected by an array of factors; including the organizational policies, procedures, cultural values and assumptions. Hence, the need to recognize where revisions and retraining is required to encourage collaboration, communication, and trust (Montero & Montero, 2010, p. 13). The transition will be further complicated by known issues in the virtual environment; i.e. time zone differences, challenges in team building due to the depersonalized nature of online communication, misinterpretations of electronic messages, and so on (Zeller, n.d.). Thereby, also requiring the development of a strategy for following-up on communication, and adhering to guidelines that address these issues, as well (Montero & Montero, 2010, p. 13)(Zeller, n.d.).

Point #3:

Mary Parker Follett: Business Units: Functional Whole or Integrative Unity

"It seems to me that the first test of business administration, of industrial organization, should be whether you have a business with all its parts so coordinated, so moving together in their closely knit and adjusting activities, so linking,

interlocking, interrelating, that they make a working unit--that is, not a congeries of separate pieces--but what I have called a functional whole or integrative unity" (Fox & Urwick, Eds.,1982, p. 42).

Current Business Challenge: Organizational Design in an Evolving Internal and External Environment

Organizational design is defined as “the manner in which a management achieves the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization’s operations, in response to the level of uncertainty in its external environment” (Business Dictionary.com, n.d.). In addition, it is defined as “a formal process of integrating people, information and technology together in the right mix to achieve objectives” (Study.com, n.d.) (Zeller, Summer 2018).

In the evolving global economy, design often transcends the boundaries of organizations; e.g. to ‘fit’ international / regional / local laws, politics, cultures, and geography (Brewster, Sparrow, & Vernon, 2007; and Edwards, 2004) (Zeller, Summer 2018). Moreover, in order to maintain the right combination of differentiation and integration, organizations will have to continually ‘fit’ both internal design and structure; in a variety of business-related environments.

Point #4:

Mary Parker Follett: Centralized / Decentralized Control

"Any over-emphasis on ultimate control disregards one of the most important trends in the recent development of thinking on organization: 'central control' used to mean the chief executive; now it is a technical expression of scientific management indicating the point where knowledge and experience on the matter in question are brought to a focus" (Fox & Urwick, Eds.,1982, p 124).

Current Business Challenge: Decentralization in the Hybrid (Virtual / Traditional) Workplace

The study by Zoghi, Mohr, and Meyer (2010) regarding the decentralization of decision-making and information-sharing is applicable to the dynamics of the hybrid work environment. Though the results offered no clear indication as to the association with decentralization and information-sharing to changes of the existing work processes, they did shed light on just a few of the questions that need to be considered when introducing a hybrid work policy and subsequent changes (Zoghi, Mohr, & Meyer, 2010, p. 634)(Zeller, 2017).

Point #5:

Mary Parker Follett: Power Over - Power With

Mary Parker Follett, who believed that management was the art of getting things done through people, proposed an idea: it is not where work takes place but to “focus on the science of getting people to cooperate”; instead of “power over, believe that genuine power is power with” (Mele & Rosanas, 2003) (Zeller, 2018 Fall) (See e.g. Fox & Urwick, Eds.,1982, p 72).

Current Business Challenge: Organizational Management in the Hybrid (Virtual / Traditional) Workplace

Today, whether the workplace is a virtual work-from-home setting or a traditional ‘brick and mortar’ office, the workforce is scattered. Wayne Turmel, co-founder of the Remote Leadership Institute, which helps managers deal with a scattered workforce, said many companies expanded working from home options for financial reasons; however, they didn't adjust their remote work approach to balance remote work with collaboration or getting people to cooperate (Lee, 2016)(Zeller, 2018 Fall).

Summary

Notably, the preceding section, Discussion Points, is just a snippet of the wealth of information that can be gleaned from Mary Parker Follett's work.

Her two fundamental concepts, evident throughout her research, speeches. and writing, are: universal fact, recognizes the mutual influence, the scope of relationships and their bearing on the participants' thinking; and universal goals, as the integration or differences which come together in a way that produces a new form.

Mary Parker Follett's concepts of universal fact (mutual influence) and universal goals (integration) are as applicable to today's organizations as they were when first written. Her research selected for the discussion points continues to be relevant: (1) identifying real issues in a situation; (2) delivering communication to a widely scattered workforce; (3) coordinating and unifying business units; (4) decentralizing control of knowledge and experience; and (5) where work takes place is not a factor in getting things done.

Essentially, her research provides the foundation for understanding how to proceed in an evolving, complex business climate without losing sight of the dual importance of understanding mutual influence and the situation: "We should notice too, what is sometimes forgotten, that in the social situation two processes always go on together: the adjustment of man and man, and the adjustment of man and the situation" (Follett, 1951, p 122). Without doing so, there may be missed opportunities for integration and unity to achieve new forms.

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